

A geometry of fermions

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***Context & disclaimer.** This study was conducted outside my primary field of expertise and outside working hours. It began as a Saturday-night exploration of a fermionic puzzle, which gradually evolved into a coherent system and, eventually, a tentative law whose results became too intriguing to leave unpublished. I acknowledge the lack of formal theoretical rigor, as the approach is purely geometrical — a feature that can be considered both a strength and a limitation. This work was carried out independently, in an effort to preserve a fresh perspective and explore the geometrical patterns as far as possible. I hope the community will receive this initiative with openness and understanding — taking what is useful, rejecting what is flawed, and, where possible, integrating it into the rigorous foundations of the Standard Model.*

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Abstract

Longstanding questions in the Standard Model's fermionic sector — including the unexplained diversity and origin of quantum numbers, the fermion mass hierarchy, and the mechanism generating neutrino masses — are addressed through a purely geometrical, phenomenological framework. The construction relies solely on experimental inputs — measured fermion masses and quantum assignments — and introduces four discrete numbers, or *seeds* (n, k, n', k') , from which both quantum numbers and mass relations emerge. Quantum numbers are expressed as second-order polynomials in (k, k') , while fermion masses follow a universal exponential law depending only on the seeds and six constants $(m_e, \alpha, \beta, \alpha', \beta', \lambda)$. With the electron mass m_e fixed as reference, all known fermion masses are reproduced within instrumental uncertainties, showing that a six-parameter model suffices to capture the full hierarchy. The framework extends naturally to the case of Dirac-type neutrinos: a geometrical singularity in the limit $1/Y_R \rightarrow \infty$ with Y_R the right-handed hypercharge allows generation of extremely small masses consistent with current observations. Flavor mixing — in the Cabibbo–Kobayashi–Maskawa (CKM) and Pontecorvo–Maki–Nakagawa–Sakata (PMNS) matrices — emerges from transitions in the (n, k) seed space, offering a unified geometrical explanation of quark and lepton flavor structures. Three main predictions arise. (i) A new charged lepton with electron-like properties and predicted mass $8.5938^{+0.0004}_{-0.0004}$ MeV. Remarkably, a 2024 experimental report (Anikina, Nikitin & Rikhvitsky, 2024) observed a lepton-like state at 8.5 ± 2.5 MeV, which they named the anomalon (a^-), consistent with this prediction. This observation, if confirmed, would constitute the first experimental validation of the geometrical mass framework. (ii) A third fermionic branch, the leonids, emerges for extended seed values, hinting at hidden or dark sectors. (iii) A fourth branch, the apex, restores gauge anomaly cancellation; these states carry color 8, forming a fermionic counterpart of the gluons and completing the geometrical spectrum. In parallel, the natural emergence of the golden ratio φ and its conjugate φ^* in left-right symmetric states suggests a deep algebraic symmetry underlying fermionic organization. Future experimental scrutiny, particularly of the anomalon, will determine whether this geometrical framework uncovers the missing structure of matter.

Introduction

The matter content of the Standard Model (SM) consists of fermions, which include up-type quarks (up u , charm c , top t), down-type quarks (down d , strange s , bottom b), charged leptons (electron e^- , muon μ^- , tau τ^-), and their associated neutrinos (ν_e, ν_μ, ν_τ). The SM provides an accurate description of their interactions and properties, yielding predictions for observed phenomena ranging from beta decay to high-energy collider processes (Glashow, 1961). Despite its well-established success over multiple decades, the SM still leaves several fundamental questions about fermions unanswered (Altmannshofer & Greljo, 2024). In particular, four central gaps can be highlighted:

Origin of quantum numbers. In the SM, quantum numbers such as hypercharge (for left- and right-handed fermions, Y_L and Y_R), left-handed weak isospin (T_3^L), baryon number (B), and lepton number (L) are not derived from first principles; rather, they are assigned to ensure internal consistency. Their values are chosen to guarantee gauge anomaly cancellation, to preserve empirical conservation laws (such as B and L at the perturbative level, see Hooft, 1976), to determine the embedding of fermions within $SU(2)$ doublets (via the weak isospin T_3^L) and to reproduce the observed electric charges (Q) of the fermions. However, the SM provides no deeper explanation for how these particular quantum numbers emerge.

Fermion masses and Yukawa couplings. In the SM, fermion masses originate from Yukawa interactions with the Higgs field after electroweak symmetry breaking (Higgs, 1964). However, the Yukawa couplings themselves are arbitrary free parameters, fixed empirically for each particle (Weinberg, 1967). Thus, while the SM accommodates the observed fermion masses, it does not predict them, leaving the origin of the mass hierarchies and the pattern of three generations unexplained.

Neutrinos. Neutrinos pose a fundamental challenge to the SM, as their unique properties are not naturally accommodated within the framework. They are the only fermions in the SM with vanishing electric charge ($Q = 0$). In the minimal SM they are strictly massless, since right-handed neutrino fields are absent and no Yukawa couplings to the Higgs can be written. Experimentally, however, neutrino oscillations demonstrate that neutrinos have nonzero but extremely small masses, many orders of magnitude below those of charged fermions (Fukuda et al., 1998). This discrepancy indicates that the SM is incomplete and suggests the existence of new physics, such as right-handed neutrinos or alternative mass-generation mechanisms (e.g. seesaw models, see Minkowski, 1977). This structural discrepancy between neutrinos and the other fermions challenges the SM's unified description of matter fields.

Flavor structure. The SM incorporates quark mixing through the Cabibbo–Kobayashi–Maskawa (CKM) matrix, which governs flavor-changing weak interactions (Cabibbo, 1963). While the formalism is consistent with experiment, the observed hierarchies among the CKM elements lack theoretical explanation within the SM (Kobayashi & Maskawa, 1973). The leptonic analogue is the Pontecorvo–Maki–Nakagawa–Sakata (PMNS) matrix, which describes neutrino oscillations (Maki et al., 1962). The PMNS encodes the mismatch between neutrino mass eigenstates and weak interaction eigenstates. In contrast to the CKM case, the PMNS matrix exhibits large mixing angles and a markedly different structure. At present, the SM provides no mechanism that relates the two matrices or accounts for the striking disparity between quark and lepton flavor mixing.

The aim of this study is to address these longstanding open questions in particle physics by adopting a purely phenomenological and geometrical approach constructed *solely* from the observed fermion masses and the quantum numbers. Three main results can be summarized as follows:

- **Common emergence of quantum numbers and fermion masses.** Both quantum numbers and fermion masses (captured within instrumental uncertainties) are generated by a novel set of four numbers (n, k, n', k') , referred to as *seeds*, introduced in this study. Quantum numbers are given as second-order polynomials in the variables k and k' . Fermion masses are modeled by an exponential function depending solely on (n, k, n', k') and parametrized by six constants $(m_e, \alpha, \beta, \alpha', \beta'$ and $\lambda)$. In this framework, the electron mass m_e is fixed as the reference constant (given, not predicted), from which all other fermion masses are determined.

- **Neutrino mass generation.** The mass law can be naturally extended to account for neutrino masses, thereby covering the full fermion spectrum. This is achieved through the geometrical emergence of a term proportional to $1/Y_R$, which was initially constructed for charged leptons and quarks only. For neutrinos, where $Y_R = 0$, this term behaves as a singularity, which, when properly regulated, can produce neutrino masses consistent with experimental observations. Neutrinos are therefore treated as Dirac-type particles within this framework.

- **Explanation of the CKM hierarchy.** The observed hierarchy in the CKM matrix is explained through transitions in the (n, k) space with n and k the seeds specific to the left-handed sector. The framework can be consistently extended to the PMNS matrix. This therefore provides a unified description of the quark and lepton flavor structure.

In particular, this study advances three predictions, one well-supported and the two others more speculative:

1. **A new lepton.** It predicts the existence of a new elementary charged lepton, with properties analogous to those of the electron, muon, and tau, and a mass of $8.5938^{+0.0004}_{-0.0004}$ MeV. Independently, a 2024 study reported the observation of a charged particle carrying an electron-like lepton number and a measured mass of 8.5 ± 2.5 MeV (Anikina, Nikitin & Rikhvitsky, 2024). I identify this particle with the lepton predicted here and adopt the name introduced in that study, *anomalon* (symbol a^-). This charged lepton necessarily requires a neutrino companion in this framework. If confirmed, this observation would constitute the most significant validation of the model.
2. **A third fermionic branch.** It further speculates the existence of a third fermionic branch, complementing the quarks and leptons. This new branch, referred to as the *leonids* (with their full set of properties detailed in Table 4 and Fig. 5), arises naturally from extending the seed k beyond its original range $(0, 1, 2, 3)$ to encompass $(-1, 0, 1, 2, 3, 4)$.
3. **A fourth fermionic branch.** A final branch, termed the *apex*, has been introduced to restore anomaly cancellation, which is otherwise disrupted by the inclusion of the anomalon and leonids. The apex¹ form a distinct set of fermions whose full quantum assignments and masses are detailed in Table 5 and Fig. 5.

¹ with the imposed same form in singular and plural: one apex or two apex.

The results of this study point to a deep connection between the geometrical properties of the framework and the fundamental particles and interactions of the SM, offering new insights into the underlying structure of particle physics. Remarkably, the golden ratio φ and its conjugate φ^* emerge naturally within the construction, associated with states whose left- and right-handed hypercharges are identical. Future experimental tests of the predictions derived in this study will ultimately determine whether the search for completeness should be pursued further or abandoned.

The presentation is organized as follows. First, the concept of seeds is introduced (Fig. 1, Tables 1–2). Next, the mass law and its detailed derivation are presented (Figs. 2–4, Tables 2–3), followed by an analysis of the CKM and PMNS matrices within the framework of the model. The discussion then begins by reviewing the well-supported predictions of the study, before turning to the more speculative extensions in which the leonids (Fig. 5, Table 4) and apex (Fig. 5, Table 5) are introduced to complete the geometrical structure of the framework. The final section outlines the open questions that remain in relation to the SM and presents the concluding remarks.

The seeds

The geometrical construction of the mass law (detailed in the following two sections) gives rise to four numbers n, k, n' and k' , designated in this study as *seeds*. Each fermion is associated with a quartet of seeds (n, k, n', k') . The pair (n, k) corresponds to the left-handed sector, while (n', k') corresponds to the right-handed sector. The seeds k and k' generate all known fermionic quantum numbers (see below, Table 1 and Fig. 1), while the full quartet (n, k, n', k') generates the masses of all fermions within experimental uncertainties (Table 2). The electron corresponds to $(k, n, k', n') = (0, 0, 0, 0)$ and is regarded as the origin of all fermionic masses, as required by the geometrical constraints of the system (Fig. 2).

Detailed explanation of each seed:

- The *generation seed* $n = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ is the generation number as known in the SM, with the exception of the electron and its neutrino companion ν_e , which are uniquely assigned $n = 0$.
- The *left-charge seed* $k = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ generates the left-handed hypercharge (Y_L), baryon number (B) and lepton number (L). Charged leptons are associated with $k = 0$, neutrinos are associated with $k = 3$. The up-type and down-type quarks are mixed between $k = 1$ and $k = 2$: The (u, s, b) quarks are associated with $k = 1$, and the (d, c, t) quarks are associated with $k = 2$. This permutation $k_u \leftrightarrow k_d$ is a fundamental constraint imposed by the geometry (Fig. 2).
- The *residual seed* $n' = \{-1, 0, 1\}$ has been imposed by geometry to distribute mass residuals into negative, neutral, and positive linear relations that are symmetrical (Fig. 4). No clear physical interpretation has emerged for it yet.
- The *right-charge seed* $k' = \{0, 1, 2\}$ generates the right-handed hypercharge (Y_R) and electric charge (Q). Charged leptons are associated with $k' = 0$, down-type quarks with $k' = 1$, and up-type quarks with $k' = 2$. Neutrinos are mathematically extended to the right-handed sector with $k'_\nu = \frac{-3+\sqrt{33}}{2}$ (this will impose $Y_R = 0$, see below).

All fermionic quantum numbers in the SM (Y_L, B, L, Y_R, Q, T_3) are generated from k and k' via second-order polynomials: $Y_R(k') = \frac{1}{3}k'^2 + k' - 2$; $Q(k') = \frac{1}{6}k'^2 + \frac{1}{2}k' - 1$; $Y_L(k) = -\frac{2}{3}k^2 + 2k - 1$; $B(k) = -\frac{1}{6}k^2 + \frac{1}{2}k$; $L(k) = \frac{1}{2}k^2 - \frac{3}{2}k + 1$; and $T_3^L(k, k') = \frac{1}{2}(Y_R(k') - Y_L(k))$.

Fig. 1. Polynomial formulation of the hypercharges. The left-handed hypercharge Y_L and the right-handed hypercharge Y_R can be expressed as two polynomials: $Y_L(k) = -\frac{2}{3}k^2 + 2k - 1$ and $Y_R(k') = \frac{1}{3}k'^2 + k' - 2$, with k and k' the left-charge and right-charge seeds, respectively. Right-handed neutrinos (ν_R) are depicted as an empty square at $k'_v = \frac{-3+\sqrt{33}}{2}$, arising as a mathematical extension of the system with $Y_R(k'_v) = 0$. The left-handed weak isospin is defined as $T_3^L(k, k') = \frac{1}{2}(Y_R(k') - Y_L(k))$ for which the golden ratio φ appears as a root. The symbol a corresponds to a fourth hypothetical charged lepton called the anomalon.

In this framework, the left weak isospin connects the left-handed and the right-handed sector through $T_3^L(k, k') = \frac{1}{2}(Y_R(k') - Y_L(k))$. Interestingly, for $k' = k = \varphi = \frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2}$ (the golden ratio), one finds $T_3^L(\varphi, \varphi) = 0$. At this special value, there is no distinction between left- and right-handed hypercharges due to $Y_R(\varphi) = Y_L(\varphi) = -1 + \frac{2\sqrt{5}}{3} \approx 0.4907$ (Fig. 1).

Right-handed neutrinos can be mathematically extended with $k'_\nu = \frac{-3+\sqrt{33}}{2}$, which satisfies $Y_R(k'_\nu) = 0$ and $Q(k'_\nu) = 0$. This is necessary to assign $T_3 = T_3^L(k = 3, k' = k'_\nu) = +\frac{1}{2}$ to the neutrinos, but also to generate their mass with variations around k'_ν (see the section extension to the neutrinos).

Color, being a vector property in $SU(3)$ space, is not a scalar quantum number and is not generated with the seed numbers. Finally, transforming matter into antimatter simply reverses the signs of all coefficients in the polynomials defining the quantum numbers, leaving the seeds unchanged.

	Seeds			Quantum numbers					
	k	k'		Y_L	Y_R	Q	T_3^L	L	B
e^-	0	0	→	-1	-2	-1	-1/2	1	0
a^-	0	0	→	-1	-2	-1	-1/2	1	0
μ^-	0	0	→	-1	-2	-1	-1/2	1	0
τ^-	0	0	→	-1	-2	-1	-1/2	1	0
d	2	1	→	+1/3	-2/3	-1/3	-1/2	0	+1/3
s	1	1	→	+1/3	-2/3	-1/3	-1/2	0	+1/3
b	1	1	→	+1/3	-2/3	-1/3	-1/2	0	+1/3
u	1	2	→	+1/3	+4/3	+2/3	+1/2	0	+1/3
c	2	2	→	+1/3	+4/3	+2/3	+1/2	0	+1/3
t	2	2	→	+1/3	+4/3	+2/3	+1/2	0	+1/3
ν_e	3	k'_ν	→	-1	0	0	+1/2	1	0
ν_a	3	k'_ν	→	-1	0	0	+1/2	1	0
ν_μ	3	k'_ν	→	-1	0	0	+1/2	1	0
ν_τ	3	k'_ν	→	-1	0	0	+1/2	1	0

Table 1. Generation of the quantum numbers from the seeds k and k' . The left-handed hypercharge $Y_L(k)$, the right-handed hypercharge $Y_R(k')$, the electric charge $Q(k')$, the left-handed weak isospin $T_3^L(k, k') = \frac{1}{2}(Y_R(k') - Y_L(k))$, the lepton number $L(k)$ and the baryon number $B(k)$ can be expressed as second-order polynomials taking into arguments the left-charge seed k (associated with the left-handed sector) and the right-charge seed k' (associated with the right-handed sector). The value $k'_\nu = (-3 + \sqrt{33})/2$ represents a mathematical extension of neutrinos into the right-handed sector. The symbol a^- corresponds to a fourth hypothetical charged lepton called the anomalon, with ν_a its neutrino companion.

The mass law

Presentation of the law

The following law reproduces the masses of the charged leptons and quarks within their experimental uncertainties (Table 2). Its extension to neutrinos arises naturally through the singular limit $\frac{1}{Y_R} \rightarrow \infty$, which enables the generation of extremely small masses consistent with measurements (see section extension to the neutrinos).

$$m_{\text{pred}}(n, k, n', k') = m_e e^{(k+n-3)e^{\alpha k + \beta} - 3(k-e^\beta)} \lambda^{k'+n'} \left(\alpha' \frac{k'+3}{Y_R(k')} + \beta' \right)$$

with:

- m_{pred} the predicted mass of a fermion.
- (n, k, n', k') the four seeds.
- m_e the observed mass of the electron. This value is given, not predicted.
- $Y_R(k') = \frac{1}{3}k'^2 + k' - 2$ the right-handed hypercharge
- $\alpha, \beta, \alpha', \beta'$ and λ five empirical constants (values shown in Table 3).

The anomalon: a fourth charged elementary lepton

An empty slot for a new particle appears at $(n, k, n', k') = (1, 0, 1, 0)$, corresponding to a predicted mass of $8.5938_{-0.0004}^{+0.0004}$ MeV and charge $Q(k' = 0) = -1$. A search in the literature revealed a striking candidate: Anikina, Nikitin, and Rikhvitsky (2024) reported the discovery of a charged particle of mass 8.5 ± 2.5 MeV sharing the leptonic number of an electron. They named this particle the *anomalon*, and its nature remained elusive. I adopt this terminology here, denote it by the symbol a^- associated with an observed mass of $m_a = 8.5 \pm 2.5$ MeV (Fig. 2,3,4). The anomalon has been fully integrated in the present framework, and is interpreted as a new elementary charged lepton between the electron and the muon. The anomalon necessarily requires a neutrino companion ν_a to fill the slot $(n, k) = (1, 3)$ (see section neutrinos).

	Seeds					Predicted mass	Observed mass
	n	k	n'	k'		m_{pred} (MeV)	m_{obs} (MeV)
e^-	0	0	0	0	\rightarrow	given, not predicted	$0.51099895000^{+0.00000000015}_{-0.00000000015}$
a^-	1	0	1	0	\rightarrow	$8.5938^{+0.0004}_{-0.0004}$	$8.5^{+2.5}_{-2.5}$
μ^-	2	0	-1	0	\rightarrow	$105.6583755^{+0.0000022}_{-0.0000022}$	$105.6583755^{+0.0000023}_{-0.0000023}$
τ^-	3	0	0	0	\rightarrow	$1776.93^{+0.09}_{-0.09}$	$1776.93^{+0.09}_{-0.09}$
d	1	2	1	1	\rightarrow	$4.69^{+0.01}_{-0.01}$	$4.70^{+0.07}_{-0.07}$
s	2	1	0	1	\rightarrow	$93.4^{+0.2}_{-0.2}$	$93.5^{+0.8}_{-0.8}$
b	3	1	-1	1	\rightarrow	4183^{+7}_{-7}	4183^{+7}_{-7}
u	1	1	0	2	\rightarrow	$2.18^{+0.01}_{-0.01}$	$2.16^{+0.07}_{-0.07}$
c	2	2	1	2	\rightarrow	$1273.2^{+3.1}_{-3.1}$	$1273.0^{+4.6}_{-4.6}$
t	3	2	-1	2	\rightarrow	172570^{+280}_{-280}	172570^{+290}_{-290}
Extension to the neutrinos (hypothesis: Normal Order, $m_{\nu_e} = 0$ MeV, and flavor masses presented here as mass eigenstates for simplicity.)							
ν_e	0	3	0	k'_ν	\rightarrow	0	consistent with 0 MeV
ν_a	1	3	± 1	k'_ν $\pm \epsilon_a$	\rightarrow	≥ 45600	unobserved yet
ν_μ	2	3	± 1	k'_ν $\mp \epsilon_\mu$	\rightarrow	$(0.00865^{+0.00011}_{-0.00011}) \times 10^{-6}$	$(0.00865^{+0.00011}_{-0.00011}) \times 10^{-6}$
ν_τ	3	3	± 1	k'_ν $\mp \epsilon_\tau$	\rightarrow	$(0.05013^{+0.00020}_{-0.00020}) \times 10^{-6}$	$(0.05013^{+0.00021}_{-0.00021}) \times 10^{-6}$

Table 2. Generation of the fermionic masses. All predicted masses (in MeV) are generated from the mass law $m_{\text{pred}}(n, k, n', k')$ parametrized by six constants ($m_e, \alpha, \beta, \alpha', \beta'$ and λ). Predicted values correspond to median and 2.5th and 97.5th percentiles of $\sim 10^5$ sets that individually reproduce the observed masses (PDG 2024) within experimental uncertainties (details in Table 3). The symbol a^- corresponds to a fourth hypothetical charged lepton called the anomalon (Anikina, Nikitin & Rikhvitsky, 2024), with ν_a its neutrino companion. Extension to the neutrinos (NuFit v6.0, see Esteban et al., 2024) is performed with three additional constants (ϵ_a, ϵ_μ and ϵ_τ) that regulate the singularity $\frac{1}{Y_R(k'_\nu)} \rightarrow \infty$ with $Y_R(k'_\nu) = \frac{1}{3}k'^2 + k' - 2$ the right-handed hypercharge and $k'_\nu = (-3 + \sqrt{33})/2$. For the neutrinos ν_a, ν_μ and ν_τ , the value of n' is either 1 or -1 (undetermined yet).

Fig. 2. Origin of the mass law. Three linear relationships (panel a) appear in logarithmic space with respect to natural integers. They are derived from specific ratios of observed fermionic masses given in sets A_k and B . The anomalon a (empty circle) is included with its observed mass of $m_a = 8.5$ MeV to illustrate that it fills the otherwise empty slot at $(n, k) = (1, 0)$. The slopes of these three relationships are interconnected and take the form $e^{\alpha k + \beta}$ with $k = \{0, 1, 2\}$. The final relationship (panel b) links the three lines, allowing the entire system to be expressed as $m(k, n) = m_e e^{(k+n-3)e^{\alpha k + \beta} - 3(k-e^\beta)}$. Residuals from this simplified model remain large and require further correction (Fig. 3 then Fig. 4).

Demonstration of the mass law: first part

Four linear relationships emerge when four well-chosen sets of masses are placed in a logarithmic space versus natural integers between 0 and 3 (Fig. 1a). Let $N_1 = \{0, 2, 3\}$ and $N_2 = \{1, 2, 3\}$, then the following relationships are linear (with zero intercept by construction):

with $A_0 = \{1, \frac{m_\mu}{m_e}, \frac{m_\tau}{m_e}\}$, $\log(A_0)$ versus N_1 is associated with a slope of $e^{\alpha \times 0 + \beta}$

with $A_1 = \{1, \frac{m_s}{m_u}, \frac{m_b}{m_u}\}$, $\log(A_1)$ versus (N_2-1) is associated with a slope of $e^{\alpha \times 1 + \beta}$

with $A_2 = \{1, \frac{m_c}{m_d}, \frac{m_t}{m_d}\}$, $\log(A_2)$ versus (N_2-1) is associated with a slope of $e^{\alpha \times 2 + \beta}$

with $B = \{1, \frac{m_s}{m_d}, \frac{m_\tau}{m_d}\}$, $\log(B)$ versus (N_2-1) is associated with a slope of 3

These linear relationships show that masses in each set A_k are related with an exponential action $e^{\alpha k + \beta}$ with $k = \{0, 1, 2\}$ and α, β two constants (Table 3). The integers N_1 and N_2 correspond to the generation number n , at the exception of the electron which is set to $n = 0$. The sets A_k contain all

leptons and all quarks, while the set B contains one particle of each set A_k , allowing the system to be expressed with a unique equation. After development, this system corresponds to $m(k, n) = m_e e^{(k+n-3)e^{\alpha k + \beta} - 3(k-e^\beta)}$ with $n = \{0,1,2,3\}$ the generation seed and $k = \{0,1,2\}$ the left-charge seed. Because all masses are connected with an exponential action, any other mass than the electron could have been chosen as the origin, however this particularity of $n = 0$ imposed by the system made this choice natural.

The discrepancies between the observed and predicted masses within this framework remain significant. It was therefore necessary to introduce a corrective factor, as discussed in the next section.

Fig. 3. Symmetries in the residuals. The residuals of the simplified model $m(k, n) = m_e e^{(k+n-3)e^{\alpha k + \beta} - 3(k-e^\beta)}$ are shown as $\xi = \log\left(\frac{m_{\text{observed}}}{m(k, n)}\right)$ plotted against the left-charge seed k (panel a). Clear symmetrical patterns appear, with the exception of the u and d quarks. When the k -values of these two quarks are interchanged, the symmetry is restored. This requires introducing a new seed k' (the right-charge seed, panel b), for which the up quark ($k_u = 1$ and $k'_u = 2$) and the down quark ($k_d = 2$ and $k'_d = 1$) are permuted compared to the left-charge seed k . After subtraction of the linear term $k' \log(\lambda)$ with λ a constant (Table 3), the residuals are centered in the k' space. Their full structure will be analyzed and captured in Fig. 4.

Demonstration of the mass law: second part

In order to understand how to reduce the large discrepancies produced by $m(k, n) = m_e e^{(k+n-3)e^{\alpha k + \beta} - 3(k-e^\beta)}$, the quantity $\xi = \log\left(\frac{m_{\text{observed}}}{m(k, n)}\right)$ has been computed to quantify the influence of other parameters. One remarkable relationship that emerged is $\xi(k) \sim k$ which centralizes all anomalies in the k space (Fig. 3), at the exception of two quarks: u and d . Remarkably, if the k of these two quarks is permuted, the symmetry is restored (Fig. 3). This forced the introduction of a new index k' which is equal to k at the exception of the quark up ($k_u = 1$ and $k'_u = 2$) and quark down ($k_d = 2$ and $k'_d = 1$). The index k' is identified as the right-charge seed as it has a clear physical meaning: it corresponds to the leptons ($k' = 0$), quark down-type ($k' = 1$) and quark up-type ($k' = 2$). This naturally leads to the development of the right-handed hypercharge Y_R as a polynomial of k' : $Y_R(k') = \frac{1}{3}k'^2 + k' - 2$ is the unique polynomial satisfying $Y_R(0) = -2$, $Y_R(1) = -2/3$ and $Y_R(2) =$

4/3. The law now becomes:

$$m(k, n, k') = m_e e^{(k+n-3)e^{\alpha+k\beta}-3(k-e\beta)} \lambda^{k'+\psi}$$

with λ a constant and ψ the remaining residuals. To capture them, two symmetrical linear relationships naturally appeared in χ versus $(k' + 3)/Y_R(k')$, which leads to the final law (Fig. 4):

$$m(k, n, k', n') = m_e e^{(k+n-3)e^{\alpha+k\beta}-3(k-e\beta)} \lambda^{k'+n' \left(\alpha' \frac{k'+3}{Y_R(k')} + \beta' \right)}$$

the integer $n' = \{-1, 0, 1\}$ is the residual seed, which is attributed to each particle to distribute the residuals into their respective linear relationship (Fig. 4). Table 2 provides the predicted masses versus observed masses of all quarks and leptons: they are all captured within instrumental uncertainties.

Fig. 4. Residual closure of the mass law. The residuals ψ are defined from the extended law $m(k, n, k') = m_e e^{(k+n-3)e^{\alpha+k\beta}-3(k-e\beta)} \lambda^{k'+\psi}$ developed through Fig. 2 and Fig. 3. When plotted against $(k' + 3)/Y_R(k')$ with $Y_R(k') = \frac{1}{3}k'^2 + k' - 2$ the right-handed hypercharge, three striking linear relationships appear, symmetric about $\psi = 0$. This symmetry motivates the introduction of the residual seed n' , which assigns the residuals to their respective linear families. Instrumental uncertainties are shown for the u quark and the anomalon a only, as their values deviate slightly from the predicted law. All quarks and charged leptons are captured within instrumental uncertainties.

constant	value	comment
m_e	$0.51099895000^{+0.000000000015}_{-0.000000000015}$	Value in MeV given by the PDG 2024.
α_*	$0.3379^{+0.0002}_{-0.0002}$	These values represent the median (0.5) and the 2.5th and 97.5th percentiles of $\sim 10^5$ sets of $(\alpha, \beta, \alpha', \beta'$ and $\lambda)$, each of which reproduces all observed fermion masses within their respective experimental uncertainties. The predicted masses listed in Table 2 correspond to median and 2.5th and 97.5th percentiles of all predictions from these same sets. These $\sim 10^5$ sets of $(\alpha, \beta, \alpha', \beta'$ and $\lambda)$ were drawn from a much larger Monte Carlo sample of $\sim 10^{12}$ random sets, the vast majority of which were rejected for failing to reproduce each observed mass within experimental uncertainties.
β_*	$0.999900^{+0.000006}_{-0.000006}$	
α'_*	$0.40^{+0.02}_{-0.02}$	
β'_*	$2.53^{+0.09}_{-0.09}$	
λ_*	$1.055^{+0.002}_{-0.002}$	
α	0.3378966	
β	0.9999000429	
α'	0.39745224	
β'	2.5385878	
λ	1.0552299954	
Extension to the neutrinos (hypothesis: Normal Order, Dirac-type, $m_{\nu_e} = 0$ MeV)		
ϵ_e	0	singularity leading to $m_{\nu_e} = 0$ MeV
ϵ_a	$\lesssim 0.0107428$	This ensures that $m_{\nu_a} \gtrsim 45600$ MeV
ϵ_μ	$0.00152635^{+0.00000058}_{-0.00000058}$	These values represent the median (0.5) and the 2.5th and 97.5th percentiles of $\sim 10^5$ sets of $(\epsilon_\mu, \epsilon_\tau)$, each of which reproduces observed neutrino masses within their respective experimental uncertainties.
ϵ_τ	$0.00129421^{+0.00000014}_{-0.00000014}$	

Table 3. Values of the constants. All constants used in the mass law are presented here. The set $\alpha, \beta, \alpha', \beta'$ and λ reproduces the central value (median) of the predicted masses (charged leptons and quarks) shown in Table 2. The extension to the neutrinos is performed with four additional constants ($\epsilon_e, \epsilon_a, \epsilon_\mu$ and ϵ_τ) that intervene in $k'_{\nu, \text{eff}} = k'_\nu \pm \epsilon_\nu$.

Extension to the neutrinos

Neutrinos have naturally been incorporated into the mass law following these logical steps:

(i) Neutrinos are assigned the same generation seed n as their charged-lepton companions. This is the only solution consistent with the quarks, where the two members of a doublet share the same n .

(ii) Neutrinos are assigned with the left-charge seed $k_\nu = 3$ and right-charge seed $k'_\nu = \frac{-3+\sqrt{33}}{2}$. This is the only solution consistent with the polynomial structure of the hypercharges, lepton and baryon numbers (section seed numbers and Fig. 1).

(iii) The right-handed term $\lambda^{k'+n'} \left(\alpha' \frac{k'+3}{Y_R(k')} + \beta' \right)$ acts as an ideal lever for generating neutrino masses when $Y_R \rightarrow 0$. When the sign (controlled by n') is negative, it naturally produces extremely small masses; when the sign is positive, it yields large masses, a feature that will be useful for the fourth neutrino ν_a . A vanishing mass is permitted only for a single neutrino, identified here as ν_e in the normal ordering. The indeterminacy $0 \times \infty$ in the mass formula for $n' = 0$ is leveraged by assigning $0 \times \infty \rightarrow -\infty$ to obtain $m_{\nu_e} = 0$, consistent with the observed mass hierarchy. For the other neutrinos ($n' = \pm 1$), this singularity must be regulated: this is achieved by defining $k'_{\nu,\text{eff}} = k'_\nu \pm \epsilon_\nu$, where ϵ_ν represents small flavor-dependent variations that generate the correct masses.

The point (i) strongly suggests that neutrinos follow a normal ordering (NO), dictated by the following experimental constraints (derived from NuFit data v6.0 including atmospheric data, see Esteban et al., 2024):

$$m_{\nu_e} \sim 0 \text{ eV}$$

$$m_{\nu_\mu} = m_{\nu_e} + 0.00865 (\pm 0.00011) \text{ eV}$$

$$m_{\nu_\tau} = m_{\nu_e} + 0.05013 (\pm 0.00021) \text{ eV}$$

The neutrino companion ν_a of the anomalon a must be significantly heavier (above ~ 45.6 GeV) for two main reasons:

- (1) Number of light active neutrinos: Precision measurements of the invisible width of the Z boson indicate that only three light active neutrinos exist. Any additional light neutrino would have contributed to the Z decay width and would already have been observed.
- (2) Kinematic constraint from Z decay: To avoid contributing to the total Z boson width, the anomalon's neutrino companion must have a mass greater than $\frac{m_Z}{2} \sim 45.6$ GeV, otherwise the decay $Z \rightarrow \nu_a \bar{\nu}_a$ would be allowed and experimentally detected.

The extended framework, developed through points (i)–(iii), allows all experimental and theoretical constraints to be satisfied, resulting in three neutrino masses that are consistent with observations ($m_{\nu_e}, m_{\nu_\mu}, m_{\nu_\tau}$), and a fourth hypothetical neutrino with a large mass ($m_{\nu_a} > 45.6$ GeV). The corresponding values are summarized in Table 2.

The CKM & PMNS matrices

CKM matrix

The CKM matrix is a central ingredient of the SM, describing the amplitudes for transitions from up-type to down-type quarks through the charged weak current mediated by the W^\pm bosons. Explicitly, it takes the form

$$V_{CKM} = \begin{bmatrix} V_{ud} & V_{us} & V_{ub} \\ V_{cd} & V_{cs} & V_{cb} \\ V_{td} & V_{ts} & V_{tb} \end{bmatrix}$$

with amplitude (Particle Data Group or PDG 2024):

$$|V_{CKM}| = \begin{bmatrix} 0.97435 \pm 0.00016 & 0.22501 \pm 0.00068 & 0.003732^{+0.000090}_{-0.000085} \\ 0.22487 \pm 0.00068 & 0.97349 \pm 0.00016 & 0.04183^{+0.00079}_{-0.00069} \\ 0.00858^{+0.00019}_{-0.00017} & 0.04111^{+0.00077}_{-0.00068} & 0.999118^{+0.000029}_{-0.000034} \end{bmatrix}$$

This matrix is unitary, ensuring the conservation of probability in flavor-changing processes, and its complex structure is the unique source of CP violation in the quark sector of the SM.

The Wolfenstein parametrization (Wolfenstein, 1983) revealed a striking hierarchy in the CKM elements, organized as natural powers of $\lambda_w \sim |V_{us}|$, from $\sim \lambda_w^0$ (maximum amplitudes on the diagonal) to $\sim \lambda_w^3$ (minimum amplitudes in the top right and bottom left corners). While the truncated Wolfenstein expansion (up to $O(\lambda_w^4)$) is elegant and widely used, higher-order formulations also exist (Ahn, Cheng & Oh, 2011), but quickly become cumbersome. In parallel, the SM offers no explanation for why the CKM entries follow this particular hierarchy. Another approach focusing on a description in terms of mixing angles (the “standard” parametrization) only implicitly encodes this hierarchy (Chau & Keung, 1984).

The present study aims to address these issues by proposing a simple and complete parametrization of the CKM matrix, in which the hierarchy naturally emerges from transitions in the (n, k) space, considered here as specific to the left-handed sector. This is consistent with the fact that the CKM matrix arises only in the left-handed sector, since the charged weak current couples exclusively to quark doublets of left-handed chirality (PDG, 2024).

Dattoli & Di Palma (2013) showed that the CKM matrix can be expressed as $V_{CKM} = \exp(A_{CKM})$ with A_{CKM} a generator belonging to the Lie algebra $su(3)$. In other words, A is anti-Hermitian ($A^\dagger = -A$), traceless ($Tr(A) = 0$), and thus ensures that $\exp(A)$ is a unitary matrix. In particular, their construction reproduces the truncated Wolfenstein parametrization, but also the standard parametrization. Since the logarithm of the unitary matrix V_{CKM} is not unique, there is no single choice of A , and four parameters are sufficient to entirely capture V_{CKM} (Dattoli & Di Palma, 2013). I therefore suggest the following candidate:

$$A_{CKM} = [a_{ij}^{CKM}] = b_q \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -\lambda_q & -2\lambda_q^3(x_q - iy_q) \\ \lambda_q & 0 & -\lambda_q^2 \\ 2\lambda_q^3(x_q + iy_q) & \lambda_q^2 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

with $b_q = 1.231_{-0.002}^{+0.002}$, $\lambda_q = 0.1844_{-0.0004}^{+0.0004}$, $x_q = 0.2065_{-0.0004}^{+0.0004}$, and $y_q = 0.2215_{-0.0004}^{+0.0004}$. The uncertainties correspond to a 95% confidence interval estimated with a Monte-Carlo simulation. This form reproduces $|V_{CKM}|$ within experimental uncertainties, and the computed Jarlskog invariant (capturing the CP violation, see Jarlskog, 1985) is $J = 3.12 \times 10^{-5}$, which perfectly match the $J_{\text{PDG2024}} = (3.12_{-0.12}^{+0.13}) \times 10^{-5}$. Based on a development similar to Dattoli & Di Palma (2013), an approximate analytical formulation of the Jarlskog invariant is $J \sim 2b_q^3 \lambda_q^6 y_q$, which corresponds to $J \sim 3.25 \times 10^{-5}$. The exact analytical form of J would require a complete development of V_{CKM} which is beyond the scope of this analysis. The reader should notice that $\lambda_q \neq \lambda_w$ because the goal was to reproduce a hierarchy free of assumptions, not to reproduce the Wolfenstein parametrization that postulates that the hierarchy is necessarily carried by $|V_{us}|$.

Now, the next step is to connect A to transitions in the (n, k) space dedicated to the left-handed sector from which the CKM matrix arises. Let me define four matrices $n^{(\text{up-type})}$, $n^{(\text{down-type})}$, $k^{(\text{up-type})}$ and $k^{(\text{down-type})}$ such as:

$$\begin{cases} w^{(\text{up-type})} = [w_{ij}^{(\text{up-type})}] = \begin{bmatrix} w_u & w_u & w_u \\ w_c & w_c & w_c \\ w_t & w_t & w_t \end{bmatrix} \\ w^{(\text{down-type})} = [w_{ij}^{(\text{down-type})}] = \begin{bmatrix} w_d & w_s & w_b \\ w_d & w_s & w_b \\ w_d & w_s & w_b \end{bmatrix} \end{cases}$$

with $w = n$ or $w = k$ (values in Table 2). These matrices represent the CKM structure, where each row corresponds to an up-type quark and each column corresponds to a down-type quark. It appears that the candidate A can be entirely characterized by:

$$\begin{cases} a_{ij}^{CKM} = -b_q (n_{ij}^{(\text{down-type})} - n_{ij}^{(\text{up-type})}) \lambda_q^{d_{ij}} z_q^{-\delta_{3j}\delta_{i1}} z_q^{\delta_{1j}\delta_{3i}} \\ d_{ij} = 2|n_{ij}^{(\text{down-type})} - n_{ij}^{(\text{up-type})}| + |k_{ij}^{(\text{down-type})} - k_{ij}^{(\text{up-type})}| - 1 \end{cases}$$

with $z_q = x_q + iy_q$ and δ_{ij} the Kronecker symbol. Remarkably, d_{ij} is similar to a weighted Manhattan distance that reproduces the hierarchy observed in the CKM:

$$D = [d_{ij}] = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 3 \\ 1 & 0 & 2 \\ 3 & 2 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

It should be noted that this particular structure of D arises specifically from the permutation $k_u \leftrightarrow k_d$ that was imposed in Fig. 2, which thus provides an independent validation of the internal consistency of the framework. Qualitatively, this hierarchy expresses the fact that the further apart the up-type and down-type flavors are, the less likely the transition occurs. Quantitatively, it is encoded in d_{ij} , which measures the ‘‘cost’’ of a transition distance in the (n, k) space. A jump by $n \rightarrow n \pm 1$ carries twice the cost of a jump by $k \rightarrow k \pm 1$ according to $d \sim 2|\Delta n| + |\Delta k| - 1$. Additionally, the anti-Hermitian and traceless structure of A is not regarded merely as a mathematical constraint only, but emerges from:

$$n^{(\text{up-type})} - n^{(\text{down-type})} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 & -2 \\ 1 & 0 & -1 \\ 2 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

This achieves to prove the connection between the CKM and transitions in the (n, k) space.

PMNS matrix

The PMNS matrix is the leptonic counterpart of the CKM matrix, encoding the amplitudes for transitions from charged leptons to neutrino mass eigenstates through the charged weak current mediated by the bosons W^\pm . Explicitly, it takes the following form (indices 1, 2, 3 are replaced by ν_e, ν_μ and ν_τ as each label denotes a single neutrino state, analogous to quark notation):

$$V_{PMNS} = \begin{bmatrix} V_{e\nu_e} & V_{e\nu_\mu} & V_{e\nu_\tau} \\ V_{\mu\nu_e} & V_{\mu\nu_\mu} & V_{\mu\nu_\tau} \\ V_{\tau\nu_e} & V_{\tau\nu_\mu} & V_{\tau\nu_\tau} \end{bmatrix}$$

with amplitude (simplified from NuFit 6.0 with atmospheric data, see Esteban et al., 2024):

$$|V_{PMNS}| = \begin{bmatrix} 0.822^{+0.020}_{-0.020} & 0.550^{+0.031}_{-0.031} & 0.149^{+0.007}_{-0.007} \\ 0.377^{+0.125}_{-0.125} & 0.588^{+0.092}_{-0.092} & 0.704^{+0.052}_{-0.052} \\ 0.397^{+0.121}_{-0.121} & 0.579^{+0.094}_{-0.094} & 0.690^{+0.053}_{-0.053} \end{bmatrix}$$

As in the quark sector, unitarity ensures probability conservation, but in contrast to the CKM matrix, the PMNS entries display no strong hierarchical pattern: all elements are of comparable size, with large mixing between flavors. This feature underlies the phenomenon of neutrino oscillations and points to a qualitatively different flavor structure in the lepton sector, for which the SM offers no explanation.

In this study, the exponential parametrization of the CKM matrix has been mimicked for the PMNS with success by simply replacing the (n, k) indices associated with the down-type (resp. up-type) quarks with the neutrinos (resp. charged leptons). The four matrices $n^{(\text{charged-leptons})}$, $n^{(\text{neutrinos})}$, $k^{(\text{charged-leptons})}$ and $k^{(\text{neutrinos})}$ are defined as:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} w^{(\text{charged-leptons})} = [w_{ij}^{(\text{charged-leptons})}] = \begin{bmatrix} w_e & w_e & w_e \\ w_\mu & w_\mu & w_\mu \\ w_\tau & w_\tau & w_\tau \end{bmatrix} \\ w^{(\text{neutrinos})} = [w_{ij}^{(\text{neutrinos})}] = \begin{bmatrix} w_{\nu_e} & w_{\nu_\mu} & w_{\nu_\tau} \\ w_{\nu_e} & w_{\nu_\mu} & w_{\nu_\tau} \\ w_{\nu_e} & w_{\nu_\mu} & w_{\nu_\tau} \end{bmatrix} \end{array} \right.$$

with $w = n$ or $w = k$ (values in Table 2). The structure directly parallels that of the CKM mixing matrix:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} a_{ij}^{PMNS} = -b_v \left(n_{ij}^{(\text{neutrinos})} - n_{ij}^{(\text{charged-leptons})} \right) \lambda_v^{d_{ij}} \bar{z}_v^{\delta_{3j}} \delta_{i1} z_v^{\delta_{1j}} \delta_{3i} \\ d_{ij} = 2 |n_{ij}^{(\text{neutrinos})} - n_{ij}^{(\text{charged-leptons})}| + |k_{ij}^{(\text{neutrinos})} - k_{ij}^{(\text{charged-leptons})}| - 1 \end{array} \right.$$

which correspond to:

$$A_{PMNS} = [a_{ij}^{PMNS}] = b_\nu \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -2\lambda_\nu^6 & -3\lambda_\nu^8(x_\nu - iy_\nu) \\ 2\lambda_\nu^6 & 0 & -\lambda_\nu^4 \\ 3\lambda_\nu^8(x_\nu + iy_\nu) & \lambda_\nu^4 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

The PMNS is reproduced within experimental uncertainties with the constant $b_\nu = b_q = 1.231$, $y_\nu = y_q = 0.2215$, $x_\nu = 2.2643$ and $\lambda_\nu = 0.8602$. Only x_ν and λ_ν have changed from the CKM case, which was necessary to mitigate the hierarchical pattern (λ_ν is closer to 1). The computed modules correspond to:

$$|V_{PMNS}| = \begin{bmatrix} 0.827 & 0.544 & 0.142 \\ 0.300 & 0.640 & 0.707 \\ 0.475 & 0.543 & 0.693 \end{bmatrix}$$

The reader should notice that the very large uncertainties of the PMNS matrix allow for various forms of A_{PMNS} to match the target matrix, and this apparent success might be an artificial construct. The key finding here is that the CKM structure defined in the (n, k) space remains compatible when applied to the PMNS matrix.

Discussion and extension

Before addressing potential conflicts with the SM, it is important to clearly state the main claims of this work. The claims are presented in two groups: first the strong, well-supported claims for the known fermions (**C**), followed by more speculative claims (**SC**) that predict two new fermionic branches (the leonids and the apex) by extending this framework. The discussion then proceeds to list the open questions (**O**), followed by a conclusion.

Supported claims

C1. Four seeds per fermion. Each fermion is associated with four *seeds* (Table 2), which generate both its quantum numbers and its mass (except for the electron). The seeds (n, k) correspond to the left-handed sector, while the seeds (n', k') correspond to the right-handed sector.

C2. Emergence of quantum numbers. Quantum numbers emerge from second-order polynomials taking into argument the left-charge seed k and/or right-charge seed k' : $Y_R(k') = \frac{1}{3}k'^2 + k' - 2$; $Q(k') = \frac{1}{6}k'^2 + \frac{1}{2}k' - 1$; $Y_L(k) = -\frac{2}{3}k^2 + 2k - 1$; $B(k) = -\frac{1}{6}k^2 + \frac{1}{2}k$; $L(k) = \frac{1}{2}k^2 - \frac{3}{2}k + 1$ and $T_3^L(k, k') = \frac{1}{2}(Y_R(k') - Y_L(k))$.

In this framework, quantum numbers are no longer treated as fundamental; instead, they emerge from a deeper underlying structure. Antimatter corresponds to reversing the sign of each coefficient.

C3. Mass law. All fermionic masses emerge from the following law:

$$m_{\text{pred}}(n, k, n', k') = m_e e^{(k+n-3)e^{\alpha k + \beta} - 3(k-e^\beta)} \lambda^{k'+n'} \left(\alpha' \frac{k'+3}{Y_R(k')} + \beta' \right)$$

with m_e the observed mass of the electron and $\alpha, \beta, \alpha', \beta'$ and λ five empirical constants (Table 3).

C4. The electron as reference. The electron is no longer considered part of the first generation. Instead, it serves as the fundamental reference point of the entire fermionic realm, characterized by vanishing seeds. Its mass is not emergent but is treated as a fundamental constant. This aligns with the fact that the electron is the only fermion that is stable and does not undergo decay. All other fermions are unstable and decay into lighter ones, a process which corresponds to transitions between seeds. Within this framework, all fermions can be interpreted as excitations of the electron in the underlying seed space, with their masses and properties corresponding to specific seed configurations.

C5. The anomalon. A new elementary lepton, the anomalon, shares the same quantum numbers as other charged leptons (lepton number, baryon number, electric charge, right- and left-handed hypercharges). Its mass is predicted to be $8.5938_{-0.0004}^{+0.0004}$ MeV and was most likely observed in 2024 (Anikina, Nikitin & Rikhvitsky, 2024), prior to the prediction. An associated neutrino companion is necessary otherwise the slot $(n, k) = (1, 3)$ would remain open. The nature of this neutrino (either sterile or active) remains unknown.

C6. Neutrino masses. The extremely small masses of the neutrinos originate from a singularity related to the right-handed hypercharge in $1/Y_R$ (or possibly the electric charge Q as they are related by $Q = Y_R/2$). Neutrinos follow the same generation as their charged lepton companions.

C7. CKM hierarchy. The weighted Manhattan distance $d_{ij} = 2|n_i - n_j| + |k_i - k_j| - 1$ provides a quantitative measure of the relative suppression of flavor-changing transitions between quarks i and j in the (n, k) seed space, effectively encoding the observed hierarchy of the CKM matrix elements.

Speculative claims

SC1. A third fermionic branch: the leonids. This new fermionic branch (Fig. 5, Table 4) would exist in $k = (-1, 4)$ alongside the quarks (mixed between the up-type and down-type quarks at $k = 1$ and $k = 2$) and the leptons (charged leptons at $k = 0$ and neutrinos at $k = 3$). Two numerical coincidences motivate the exploration of $k = (-1, 4)$. First, $T_3^L(-1, -1) = +\frac{1}{2}$, which is highly nontrivial since it arises from the difference between two polynomials that previously satisfy $T_3^L(0, 0) = -\frac{1}{2}$, $T_3^L(1, 1) = -\frac{1}{2}$ and $T_3^L(2, 2) = +\frac{1}{2}$ (see Fig. 5). The second coincidence is that $Y_L(-1)$ and $Y_L(4)$ are both equal to $-\frac{11}{3}$. This speculation is summarized in Table 4 and predicts six new particles (three with imaginary masses) that are neither leptons nor quarks. This new branch is named the *leonids* (singular: one leonid), and it mimics the quarks and leptons in its structure (left-handed doublets, right-handed singlets, and $T_3^L = \pm\frac{1}{2}$). The leonids are composed of three *lions* – galion (Λ_g), melion (Λ_m) and solion (Λ_s) - associated with $T_3^L = +\frac{1}{2}$ (three fermions with real masses). Their companions are the three *chimeras* — griffin (χ_g), manticore (χ_m), and sphinx (χ_s) — associated with $T_3^L = -\frac{1}{2}$ (three fermions with complex masses). These names come from the fact that the three chimeras do not exist in the real world (imaginary mass) but are all composed of body parts of lions. Chimeras are natural

candidates for the dark sector, as they possess complex masses due to their right-charge seed $k'_\chi = \frac{-3+i\sqrt{23}}{2}$ that verifies $Y_R(k'_\chi) = Y_L(4) + 2T_3^L = -\frac{11}{3} - 1 = -\frac{14}{3}$. This extension is similar to the right-handed neutrinos extension for the leptons, where $k'_\nu = \frac{-3+\sqrt{33}}{2}$ verified $Y_R(k'_\nu) = Y_L(3) + 2T_3^L = -1 + 1 = 0$. The leonids are necessarily colorless for the gauge anomaly cancellation performed in SC2.

names		seeds			predicted mass (MeV)			quantum numbers					
leonids		n	k	k'	if $n' = -1$	if $n' = 0$	if $n' = 1$	Y_L	Y_R	Q	T_3^L	L	B
lions	galion Λ_g	1	-1	-1	89.30 ± 0.27	100.73 ± 0.32	113.62 ± 0.38	$-\frac{11}{3}$	$-\frac{8}{3}$	$-\frac{4}{3}$	$+\frac{1}{2}$	3	$-\frac{2}{3}$
	melion Λ_m	2	-1	-1	620.6 ± 1.6	700.1 ± 1.9	789.7 ± 2.3	$-\frac{11}{3}$	$-\frac{8}{3}$	$-\frac{4}{3}$	$+\frac{1}{2}$	3	$-\frac{2}{3}$
	solion Λ_s	3	-1	-1	4313.4 ± 9.4	4865 ± 11	5488 ± 13	$-\frac{11}{3}$	$-\frac{8}{3}$	$-\frac{4}{3}$	$+\frac{1}{2}$	3	$-\frac{2}{3}$
chimeras	griffin χ_g	1	4	k'_χ	(1.16 ± 0.03) 10^7 $+ i(1.63$ $\pm 0.02)$ 10^6	(1.32 ± 0.03) 10^7 $+ i(1.71$ $\pm 0.03)$ 10^6	(1.50 ± 0.04) 10^7 $+ i(1.79$ $\pm 0.04)$ 10^6	$-\frac{11}{3}$	$-\frac{14}{3}$	$-\frac{7}{3}$	$-\frac{1}{2}$	3	$-\frac{2}{3}$
	manticore χ_m	2	4	k'_χ	(4.19 ± 0.14) 10^{11} $+ i(5.93$ $\pm 0.08)$ 10^{10}	(4.78 ± 0.16) 10^{11} $+ i(6.22$ $\pm 0.09)$ 10^{10}	(5.45 ± 0.18) 10^{11} $+ i(6.49$ $\pm 0.10)$ 10^{10}	$-\frac{11}{3}$	$-\frac{14}{3}$	$-\frac{7}{3}$	$-\frac{1}{2}$	3	$-\frac{2}{3}$
	sphinx χ_s	3	4	k'_χ	(1.52 ± 0.07) 10^{16} $+ i(2.15$ $\pm 0.04)$ 10^{15}	(1.74 ± 0.07) 10^{16} $+ i(2.26$ $\pm 0.04)$ 10^{15}	(1.98 ± 0.09) 10^{16} $+ i(2.36$ $\pm 0.04)$ 10^{15}	$-\frac{11}{3}$	$-\frac{14}{3}$	$-\frac{7}{3}$	$-\frac{1}{2}$	3	$-\frac{2}{3}$

Table 4. Characteristics of the leonids. The names, symbols, seeds, predicted mass and quantum numbers of the new fermionic branch called the *leonids* (partitioned into the *lions* and the *chimeras*) are summarized here. Because n' is unknown (distributed between $-1, 0$ and 1), there are three possibilities for the mass of each leonid. Predicted masses correspond to median and 2.5th and 97.5th percentiles of predictions from $\sim 10^5$ sets of $(\alpha, \beta, \alpha', \beta'$ and $\lambda)$ that individually reproduce the observed masses of known fermions (PDG 2024) within experimental uncertainties (details in Table 3). The value $k'_\chi = (-3 + i\sqrt{23})/2$ is set to verify $Y_R(k'_\chi) = -14/3$ and respect the structure of $T_3^L = \pm 1/2$. The complex seed k'_χ leads to complex masses through the mass law, which make chimeras natural candidates for the dark sector. The leonids are necessarily colorless to cancel the gauge anomalies (see SC2).

SC2. A fourth fermionic branch: the apex. This fourth fermionic branch (Fig. 5, Table 5) has been introduced to cancel the gauge anomalies (see the script in the supplementary). In the SM, the cancellation of gauge anomalies is essential to ensure the internal consistency and renormalizability of the theory. In particular, four types of anomalies must vanish: the cubic $U(1)_Y$ anomaly ($\sum Y^3$ over all fermions), the mixed $SU(2)_L^2 - U(1)_Y$ anomaly ($\sum Y$ over left-handed doublets only), the $SU(3)_C^2 - U(1)_Y$ anomaly ($\sum Y$ over all colored fermions), and the gravitational- $U(1)_Y$ anomaly ($\sum Y$ over all fermions). The traditional SM anomaly budget has been disturbed by the introduction of the anomalon and its neutrino companion (leading to four generations of leptons instead of three) and the leonids, which is a new colorless fermionic branch containing three generations of fermions (see SC1). At least

one new fermionic branch is required to cancel these disruptions. Geometrically, a remarkable point is located at $k = k_A = 3/2$ (see Fig. 5) and corresponds to the maximum left-handed hypercharge ($Y_L = \frac{1}{2}$). The value of $Y_L = \frac{1}{2}$ can be used to construct a doublet, with an upper member associated with $Y_R = Y_L + 1 = \frac{3}{2}$ and lower member associated with $Y_R = Y_L - 1 = -\frac{1}{2}$. Let me call this speculative fermionic branch the *apex* (using here apex for both singular and plural: one apex, two apex), with its upper members referred to as the *high-type apex* (symbol Δ , $T_3^L = +\frac{1}{2}$) and the lower members as the *low-type apex* (symbol ∇ , $T_3^L = -\frac{1}{2}$) to mimic the quarks. When assigning three generations to the apex (see details in Table 5) and giving them a color representation of 8 (analogous to the gluons), **all gauge anomalies are cancelled** (see supplementary). This gauge anomaly cancellation is remarkable because it occurs across three generations of leonids, quarks, and apex, but four generations of leptons.

Fig. 5. Two new fermionic branches: the leonids and the apex. The left-handed and right-handed hypercharge polynomials presented in Fig. 1 have been extended to the values $k = -1$ and $k = 4$ and lead to $Y_L(-1) = Y_L(4) = -11/3$. Coincidentally, $T_3^L(-1, -1) = +\frac{1}{2}$ which suggests that this extension could be attributed to a new fermionic branch named the *leonids*. The leonids are partitioned between the *lions* ($k = -1$, $T_3^L(-1, -1) = +\frac{1}{2}$) and the *chimeras* ($k = 4$, $T_3^L(4, k'_\chi) = -\frac{1}{2}$) with $k'_\chi = (-3 + i\sqrt{23})/2$. The golden ratio φ and its conjugate φ^* appear at the intersection between Y_L and Y_R . A last fermionic branch (the *apex*) located at $(k, Y_L) = (\frac{3}{2}, \frac{1}{2})$ has been introduced to entirely cancel the gauge anomalies (see section SC2).

names		seeds			predicted mass (MeV)			quantum numbers					
apex		n	k	k'	if $n' = -1$	if $n' = 0$	if $n' = 1$	Y_L	Y_R	Q	T_3^L	L	B
high-type	high Δ_h	1	$\frac{3}{2}$	k'_Δ	1.878 ± 0.011	2.313 ± 0.011	2.850 ± 0.012	$+\frac{1}{2}$	$+\frac{3}{2}$	$+\frac{3}{4}$	$+\frac{1}{2}$	$-\frac{1}{8}$	$+\frac{3}{8}$
	rise Δ_r	2	$\frac{3}{2}$	k'_Δ	171.03 ± 0.72	210.69 ± 0.68	259.55 ± 0.78	$+\frac{1}{2}$	$+\frac{3}{2}$	$+\frac{3}{4}$	$+\frac{1}{2}$	$-\frac{1}{8}$	$+\frac{3}{8}$
	zenith Δ_z	3	$\frac{3}{2}$	k'_Δ	15578 ± 44	19191 ± 40	23642 ± 56	$+\frac{1}{2}$	$+\frac{3}{2}$	$+\frac{3}{4}$	$+\frac{1}{2}$	$-\frac{1}{8}$	$+\frac{3}{8}$
low-type	low ∇_l	1	$\frac{3}{2}$	k'_∇	2.2808 ± 0.0059	2.1947 ± 0.0062	2.1119 ± 0.0097	$+\frac{1}{2}$	$-\frac{1}{2}$	$-\frac{1}{4}$	$-\frac{1}{2}$	$-\frac{1}{8}$	$+\frac{3}{8}$
	fall ∇_f	2	$\frac{3}{2}$	k'_∇	207.75 ± 0.45	199.91 ± 0.28	192.36 ± 0.61	$+\frac{1}{2}$	$-\frac{1}{2}$	$-\frac{1}{4}$	$-\frac{1}{2}$	$-\frac{1}{8}$	$+\frac{3}{8}$
	nadir ∇_n	3	$\frac{3}{2}$	k'_∇	18923 ± 59	18209 ± 20	17522 ± 36	$+\frac{1}{2}$	$-\frac{1}{2}$	$-\frac{1}{4}$	$-\frac{1}{2}$	$-\frac{1}{8}$	$+\frac{3}{8}$

Table 5. Characteristics of the apex. The names, symbols, seeds, predicted mass and quantum numbers of the new fermionic branch called the *apex* (partitioned into the *high-type* apex and the *low-type* apex) are summarized here. Because n' is unknown (distributed between $-1, 0$ and 1), there are three possibilities for the mass of each apex. Predicted masses correspond to median and 2.5th and 97.5th percentiles of predictions from $\sim 10^5$ sets of $(\alpha, \beta, \alpha', \beta'$ and $\lambda)$ that individually reproduce the observed masses of known fermions (PDG 2024) within experimental uncertainties (details in Table 3). The value $k'_\Delta = (-3 + \sqrt{51})/2$ and $k'_\nabla = (-3 + \sqrt{27})/2$ are set to respect the structure of $T_3^L = \pm 1/2$. The apex have necessarily a color representation of 8 to cancel the gauge anomalies (see SC2).

SC3. A primary charge seed κ . This SC3 assumes SC1 to be valid, and the claim is that $\kappa = \{-1, 0, 1\}$ (denoted as the “charge seed”) is sufficient to produce all left-charge and right-charge seeds of the leonids, leptons and quarks. The apex and the golden ratios φ and φ^* seem to emerge from a different mechanism (see section O2). Currently, the left-charge and right-charge seed values span a wide range: $k = -1$ to 4 (including the leonids), $k' = -1, 0, 1, 2$ and suddenly $k'_\nu = \frac{-3+\sqrt{33}}{2}$ and $k'_\chi = \frac{-3+i\sqrt{23}}{2}$. This likely points to a deeper mechanism generating such diversity in seed values. From this

hypothesis, two functions naturally arise: $f_L(k) = 3 - k$ and $f_R(k') = \frac{-3+\sqrt{-20k'^2+36k'+33}}{2}$. The left-charge and right-charge seeds of each doublet’s members are connected to κ through the f_L and f_R transformations:

- leonids: the lion doublets are associated with $(k, k') = (-1, -1)$, while the chimera doublets are associated with $(k, k') = (4, k'_\chi) = (f_L(-1), f_R(-1))$. Chimeras correspond to the lions under (f_L, f_R) applied to -1 .

- leptons: the charged lepton doublets are associated with $(k, k') = (0, 0)$, while the neutrino doublets are associated with $(k, k') = (3, k'_\nu) = (f_L(0), f_R(0))$. Neutrinos correspond to the charged-leptons under (f_L, f_R) applied to 0 .

- quarks: the down-type doublets are associated with $(k, k') = (1, 1)$, while the up-type doublets are associated with $(k, k') = (2, 2) = (f_L(1), f_R(1))$. Up-type quarks correspond to the down-type quarks under (f_L, f_R) applied to 1 .

The down quark and the up quark are an exception: $(k, k') = (2, 1)$ and $(k, k') = (1, 2)$, respectively. However, this exception is handled by the fact that $f_L(2) = 1$ and $f_R(2) = 1$, which is remarkable! Even more remarkably, f_R verifies that $f_R(\varphi) = \varphi$ and $f_R(\varphi^*) = \varphi^*$ and f_L verifies that $f_L(k_A) = k_A$ with $k_A = \frac{3}{2}$ the unique left-charge seed of the apex. Therefore, the three seeds that have been left out — k_A , φ and φ^* — are invariant either under f_L or f_R . These coincidences are reported in the section O2.

It has just been proven that $\kappa = \{-1, 0, 1\}$ is sufficient to produce all charge seeds of the leonids, leptons and quarks. This suggests an *emergence* of the chimeras, neutrinos and up-type quarks from their other half (see SC4).

SC4. After symmetry breaking in a pre-chiral space, chimeras emerged from lions, neutrinos from charged leptons, and up-type quarks from down-type quarks.

This SC4 assumes SC1 and SC3 to be valid. SC4 is motivated by four observations:

- (1) in the SM, fermion masses and electric charges are correlated — except for the up and down quarks. This anomaly is not explained in the SM but is interpreted here as the signature of a broken symmetry (represented by the permutation $k_u \leftrightarrow k_d$ in Fig. 2).
- (2) the generation $n = 0$ associated with (e^-, ν_e) cannot be extended to quarks due to experimental constraints — no fourth generation of quarks has been observed. This suggests that ν_e may have inherited $n = 0$ from the electron alone. Extending this reasoning to all doublets implies that each member of a doublet may have “emerged” from their other half.
- (3) the charge seed $\kappa = \{-1, 0, 1\}$ alone produces all left-charge and right-charge seeds of the leonids, quarks and leptons under the (f_L, f_R) transformation (see SC3).
- (4) there is a remarkable symmetry $k = k'$ for the lions, charged-leptons and down-type quarks. The exception is, again, the down quark and up quark, who break the symmetry between k and k' .

These observations can be unified through the following chronological narrative:

- 1) lions ($\kappa = -1$), charged-leptons ($\kappa = 0$) and down-type quarks ($\kappa = 1$) initially lived in a pre-chiral space characterized by the charge seed $\kappa = \{-1, 0, 1\}$. At this stage, they were singlets, massless, without left-handed counterparts, and the chimeras, neutrinos, and up-type quarks had not yet emerged.
- 2) A symmetry breaking occurred (associated with the permutation $k_u \leftrightarrow k_d$), during which κ split into the left-charge seed k and right-charge seed k' . This breaking marked the onset of chirality, leading to the formation of left-handed doublets. Each missing partner within a doublet subsequently emerged according to the transformations $(f_L(k), f_R(k'))$ creating the new following seed values: $k = 2, 3, 4$ and $k' = 2, k'_\nu, k'_\chi$ (see SC3). After symmetry breaking, the left-hypercharge polynomial $Y_L(x)$ became related to the right-hypercharge polynomial $Y_R(x)$ through the relation: $\phi(x) = Y_R(x) - Y_L(x)$ where $\phi(x) = x^2 - x - 1$ is the golden polynomial, satisfying $\phi(\varphi) = \phi(\varphi^*) = 0$.

The behavior of n' and n in this narrative remains undetermined at this stage, as does the role of the apex and the golden ratio φ and φ^* (see section O2). It is intriguing that $n' = \{-1, 0, 1\}$ shares the same range of values as $\kappa = \{-1, 0, 1\}$, but I do not yet understand how the generation seed n could split from n' in the same manner as the left- and right-charge seeds did from κ . If the lions exist, their n' will be determined with their mass (Table 4), and the relationship between n and n' will be easier to understand.

SC5. Chiral reorganization of Q and T_3^L . The electric charge Q and the left-handed weak isospin T_3^L cannot be expressed in terms of the left-charge seed k . Instead, Q is a purely polynomial function of the right-charge seed k' : $Q(k') = \frac{1}{6}k'^2 + \frac{1}{2}k' - 1$, while T_3^L depends on both k and k' : $T_3^L(k, k') = \frac{1}{2}(Y_R(k') - Y_L(k))$. This structure suggests the following bold claim: the electric charge Q is an intrinsic property of the right-handed sector alone, whereas the weak isospin T_3 acts as a bridge linking the left- and right-handed sectors (it could be renamed T_3^{LR}) rather than being intrinsic to the left-handed sector. If confirmed, this would compel a revision of the SM's gauge structure, reshaping our understanding of charge assignments and weak interactions.

Open questions

This section outlines a series of unresolved aspects and speculative directions emerging from the present framework. While the core structure captures the observed fermionic patterns, several elements remain only partially constrained or invite deeper interpretation beyond the established model.

O1. The physical sense of n' . The residual seed n' has been introduced to correctly account for the residuals observed in Fig. 4. The values of n' are elegantly distributed between $-1, 0$ and 1 for fermions sharing same right-handed hypercharge (fixed k'). Values of the seed n' echoes those of the charge seed $\kappa = \{-1, 0, 1\}$ (see SC4), and n' offers a right-handed counterpart to the left-handed generation seed n . However, n' is not associated with any known quantum numbers such as the hypercharges, nor with any established experimental observations, such as the three fermionic generations. The absence of clear predictive patterns for this seed leads to unresolved values for the neutrinos, leonids, and apex (Tables 2, 4, and 5). Nevertheless, it is assumed that n' can only take values in the range $-1, 0$ or 1 , consistent with all known fermions.

O2. The golden ratios φ/φ^* and the apex. The golden ratio φ and its conjugate φ^* appear twice in this study: (i) At the intersection between $Y_L(x)$ and $Y_R(x)$ in Fig. 5, and (ii) as invariants under the f_R transformation (see SC3). They are associated with a vanishing weak isospin T_3^{LR} , however, it remains unclear why irrational numbers such as φ and φ^* arise in a framework otherwise centered on natural seeds $\kappa = \{-1, 0, 1\}$ (see SC4). It is possible that these values act as seeds generating exotic states. Remarkably, postulating new vector-like particles emerging from φ and/or φ^* would not affect the gauge anomaly calculation because $Y_L(\varphi) = Y_R(\varphi)$ and $Y_L(\varphi^*) = Y_R(\varphi^*)$ and their contributions would cancel each other. This route is explored in the supplementary material with new hypothetical golden particles, the *aurions*. In parallel, apex are a construction geometrically consistent with the left-handed hypercharge Y_L of other fermions (Fig. 5) and numerically consistent with a full cancellation of the gauge anomalies. Their color charge of 8 is analogous the adjoint representation of gluons, suggesting a possible connection between the apex and gauge bosons — an idea reminiscent of supersymmetric correspondences between fermionic and bosonic degrees of freedom (Haag, Łopuszański, & Sohnius 1975). While their left-charge seed $k_A = \frac{3}{2}$ is invariant under the f_L transformation, the right-charge seeds associated with the low-type apex ($k'_V = \frac{-3+\sqrt{27}}{2}$) and high-type apex ($k'_\Delta = \frac{-3+\sqrt{51}}{2}$) are not consistent with the f_R transformation: $k'_\Delta \neq f_R(k'_V)$, unlike all other

fermionic branches. However, k'_ν and k'_Δ are expressed as $\frac{-3+\sqrt{X}}{2}$ which intriguingly mimics the structure of f_R . All these evidences suggest that apex and the golden ratios emerged from a different mechanism than the three other fermionic branches that are all constructed on the same charge seed $\kappa = \{-1,0,1\}$ (see SC3). The invariance $f_L(k_A) = k_A$, $f_R(\varphi) = \varphi$ and $f_R(\varphi^*) = \varphi^*$ may perhaps indicate — though not conclusively — that they are artefacts of the pre-chiral space postulated in SC4.

O3. The anomalon and its attached neutrino. The anomalon is a charged lepton with a mass of ~ 8.6 MeV and identical quantum numbers to those of the known charged leptons. Its existence requires an associated neutrino to occupy the $(n, k) = (1, 3)$ slot in the mass law. Experimental evidence is limited, with a single indication (Anikina, Nikitin & Rikhvitsky, 2024) from a propane bubble chamber, whose superheated liquid medium is uniquely sensitive to localized energy deposition. The particle's apparent absence in modern detectors may be explained by several speculative mechanisms: it may decay into neutral or very soft final states, travel slowly producing short tracks below detection thresholds, form neutral or weakly interacting composites, or be produced only rarely with a small cross section. These explanations are not mutually exclusive and remain untested. The nature of the associated neutrino — whether active or sterile — is entirely unknown.

O4. The leonids. The existence of the leonids raises pressing theoretical and experimental questions. The chimeras carry complex masses, implying intrinsic instability, and the doublets mix real and complex components — a structure without precedent in the SM. The predicted complex masses for the chimeras reach absurdly high values (See Table 4), far exceeding any known SM fermions, potentially approaching scales reminiscent of the primordial energies of the early universe. Such extreme mass scales may hint at a connection to physics near the Big Bang or to hidden sectors that were active only at ultra-high energies. The exotic charges, baryon/lepton assignments, and partially complex masses raise questions about the compatibility of the leonids with cosmological, astrophysical, and collider constraints. Decay channels, lifetimes, and couplings remain unconstrained, leaving experiments with minimal guidance. Yet the 2024 hint of the anomalon, consistent with this framework, suggests that previously unseen leptonic states may exist, motivating exploration of the leonids in hidden or partially decoupled sectors.

O5. Higgs mechanism. In the SM, fermion masses arise through Yukawa couplings to the Higgs field. For a fermion (f), the mass is given by $m_f = y_f \frac{v}{\sqrt{2}}$ where y_f is the Yukawa coupling (free parameter) and $v \sim 246$ GeV is the Higgs vacuum expectation value (VeV). The left- and right-handed components of the fermion are connected via the Higgs field, giving rise to the observed mass after spontaneous symmetry breaking. Within the present framework, the electron plays the role of a fundamental reference: its mass m_e is considered non-emergent and treated as a fundamental constant, thereby replacing the $\frac{v}{\sqrt{2}}$. All other fermions arise as excitations of this underlying electron field, characterized by specific seed configurations (n, k, n', k') . The mass law for all fermions naturally factorizes into a left-term $e^{(k+n-3)e^{\alpha+k\beta}-3(k-e\beta)}$ multiplied by a right-term $\lambda^{k'+n'} \left(\alpha' \frac{k'+3}{Y_R(k')} + \beta' \right)$, which resonates with the SM structure where left- and right-handed components are coupled. However, a mechanism analogous to the Higgs is required to connect the left-handed doublets with the right-handed singlets and generate mass. A possible escape route is the existence of a second Higgs boson with a VeV equal to $m_e\sqrt{2}$ that would be specific to the fermionic sector.

O6. Neutrinos. In this framework, neutrinos are naturally of Dirac type, as their right-handed components are explicitly defined through $k'_\nu = \frac{-3+\sqrt{33}}{2}$. This choice ensures that neutrinos acquire mass through the same exponential law as the charged fermions, but with a distinctive suppression factor arising from the $1/Y_R$ dependence in the exponent. At this value of k'_ν , the denominator Y_R vanishes, introducing a strong enhancement in the mass exponent that drives the neutrino masses to extremely small values. This mechanism provides a purely algebraic explanation for the observed neutrino mass hierarchy, without invoking Majorana terms or seesaw dynamics. However, two theoretical issues remain open in this approach: (i) what mechanism ensures $Y_R(k'_\nu) \neq 0$, preventing a singularity for at least two neutrinos, and (ii) how the residual seed n' is distributed among neutrino flavors.

Point (i). The simplest resolution proposed in this study introduces a small perturbation $\epsilon_\nu \ll 1$ such that $k'_{\nu,\text{eff}} = k'_\nu \pm \epsilon_\nu$, with ϵ_ν depending on the flavor (Table 3). Other formulations, however, are possible. Notably, since $f_R(\kappa) = k'_\nu$ for $\kappa = 0$ (as shown in SC3), this issue can equivalently be expressed as a perturbation on κ , namely $\kappa'_{\nu,\text{eff}} = \pm \delta_\nu$ with $\delta_\nu \ll 1$. Intuitively, the parameters δ_ν could be assumed to follow a symmetric distribution around a non-zero mean δ_{eff} (motivated by $\epsilon_\mu \neq \epsilon_\tau$ in Table 3). In this formulation, one may write $\kappa'_{\nu,\text{eff}} = \delta_{\text{eff}} \pm n' \times \delta_0$ where δ_{eff} and δ_0 are fixed constants independent of flavor, and n' determines the sign. This construction remains speculative. As long as the mechanism responsible for regulating the singular behavior of $1/Y_R$ is not identified, the problem remains open.

Point (ii). The second open question then concerns the precise assignment of the residual seed n' . While the charged leptons include two states with $n' = 0$ (the electron and the tau), the neutrinos appear to mirror this pattern only partially. The simplest resolution proposed in this study is to produce only one state $n' = 0$ assigned to ν_e , while other neutrinos follow $n' = \pm 1$. This breaks the symmetry in n' with the charged-leptons, but it better matches the experimental constraints. Alternatively, one can assign $n' = 0$ to ν_e and ν_a , and leverage the indeterminacy $0 \times \infty$ (in the term $\sim \lambda^{k'+0 \times \infty}$) by assigning $0 \times \infty \rightarrow -\infty$ to ν_e (which leads to a zero mass) and assigning $0 \times \infty \rightarrow 0$ to ν_a , which would lead to a mass of $m_{\nu_a} = 422.5 \pm 1.4$ MeV. This seems to contradict the experimental constraints on the mass of a hypothetical fourth neutrino, but this would restore the symmetry in n' .

Conclusion

All features of the proposed framework emerge from a simple yet profound geometry defined in logarithmic space. Within this construction, quantum numbers arise as second-order polynomials of two chirally oriented seeds, the left-charge seed k and right-charge seed k' . The fermion mass hierarchy is governed by an exponential law taking into arguments k and k' as well as two additional seeds: the generation seed n (associated to the left-handed sector) and the residual seed n' (associated to the right-handed sector). This law is entirely determined by six constants — $(m_e, \alpha, \beta, \alpha', \beta', \lambda)$ — from which all charged lepton and quark masses are reproduced within instrumental precision. In this framework, the electron serves as the fundamental reference state, corresponding to vanishing seeds, from which the structure of all other fermions unfolds. This six-parameter model, built solely from experimental observables, yields a concrete and falsifiable prediction: a new charged lepton, the anomalon, whose mass and properties coincide strikingly with a 2024 experimental report (Anikina, Nikitin & Rikhvitsky, 2024). While independent confirmations will be essential to establish the existence of the anomalon, the remarkable symmetry observed in the mass residuals (Fig. 4) — extending over four orders of magnitude, from ~ 10 MeV to $\sim 10^5$ MeV — strongly supports the internal consistency and non-arbitrary nature of the construction.

The framework further extends to neutrinos through a purely geometrical mechanism arising from the singular behavior of the term $\frac{1}{Y_R} \rightarrow \infty$. By introducing small, flavor-dependent shifts to the right-handed hypercharge, the singularity is regularized, naturally enabling the generation of extremely small neutrino masses consistent with current observations — without invoking additional mass scales or seesaw dynamics. This demonstrates that the same underlying geometry can, in principle, encompass the full fermionic spectrum.

In parallel, the observed hierarchy of flavor mixing in the CKM matrix emerges directly from transitions in the (n, k) seed space associated with the left-handed sector. The same mechanism extends to the PMNS matrix, reproducing the lepton mixing pattern within current experimental uncertainties. This unified treatment of mass and flavor from a single geometric principle hints at a deeper correspondence between the discrete structure of the seed space and the continuous symmetries of the SM.

The same geometrical mechanism that unifies known fermions also gives rise to a new fermionic branch, the leonids. These appear when extending the seed parameter k beyond its conventional range, to $k = -1$ and $k = 4$. At these boundary values, unexpected numerical coincidences occur: the weak isospin components $T_3^L = +\frac{1}{2}$ re-emerge at $k = -1$ purely from the quadratic structure of the quantum-number polynomials, and the corresponding left-handed hypercharge is conserved at $k = 4$. This spontaneous reconstruction of the $SU(2)$ pattern — without any additional assumptions — strongly suggests that the leonids are not arbitrary extensions, but geometrical counterparts of the SM families. Their internal doublet structure and partially complex masses indicate that they may belong to a hidden or partially decoupled sector, possibly connected to early-universe conditions where such high mass scales could be realized, or the dark sector.

Remarkably, all left- and right-charge seeds of the leonids, quarks, and leptons can be generated from a primary charge seed $\kappa = \{-1, 0, 1\}$ via the transformations f_L and f_R , which link the seeds of each member of a doublet to the seeds of its partner. In this framework, the chimeras emerge from the lions, neutrinos from the charged leptons, and up-type quarks from down-type quarks — each doublet member appearing as if it “originated” from its other half. This postulated emergence, together with

the systematic application of (f_L, f_R) , reproduces all observed charge assignments while maintaining the underlying geometric structure. This reveals a unified generative mechanism that links all fermionic doublets to the same foundational triplet κ . Moreover, these findings point to a possible pre-chiral space, characterized by the invariance of the golden ratios φ and φ^* under the f_R transformation, and by a fundamental asymmetry between the quark u ($k = 1, k' = 2$) and the quark d ($k = 2, k' = 1$). This asymmetry accounts for why electric charges in the SM correlate with fermion masses, except for these two quarks.

To maintain anomaly cancellation after introducing the anomalon and leonids, the framework requires a final branch of fermions: the apex. These states possess a color multiplicity of eight, representing the fermionic counterpart of gluons in the geometrical hierarchy. Their inclusion restores the gauge symmetries and anomaly balance of the system, completing the structure implied by the seed space. The apex thus serve a dual role — as a mathematical necessity ensuring consistency, and as a potential clue to a deeper symmetry where bosons and fermions share a common geometric origin.

Altogether, the results suggest that the apparent complexity of the fermion sector may arise from an unexpectedly simple geometrical law. If future experiments confirm the anomalon, its neutrino partner, the leonids or the apex, this framework could mark a turning point — revealing that the spectrum of matter is not arbitrary, but the imprint of an underlying geometric order.

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Code and Data Availability. The code and datasets used in this study are publicly available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17328418>.

Acknowledgments. Dedicated to my grandfather, Robert Fausser, who built a ship atop a hill in the Vosges—a vessel that never saw the sea. May this study finally set it afloat, and keep it steady against the gathering storms.

Author Contributions. F.R. was solely responsible for the conceptualization, methodology, data analysis, figure preparation, coding, and writing of this manuscript.

Competing Interests. The author declares no competing interests.

Funding. This research received no external funding.

SUPPLEMENTARY

Gauge anomaly calculation (in R language).

```
### =====
### Gauge Anomaly Cancellation – Extended Fermion Spectrum
### =====
### This script computes the  $[SU(3)]^2U(1)$ ,  $[SU(2)]^2U(1)$ ,
### Gravitational- $U(1)$ , and  $[U(1)]^3$  anomaly coefficients
### for an extended fermion set including quarks, leptons,
### leonids, and apex states.

### -----
### Parameter Definitions:
### -----
### name          : Fermion multiplet name
### Y_L, Y_R      : Left- and right-handed  $U(1)_Y$  hypercharges
### d3            : Dimension under  $SU(3)_C$  (color)
### d2            : Dimension under  $SU(2)_L$  (weak isospin)
### Dynkinindex_SU3 : Dynkin index for  $SU(3)$  representation
### Dynkinindex_SU2 : Dynkin index for  $SU(2)$  representation
### Ngenerations  : Number of fermion generations
###
### The left-right conversion is performed so that anomalies
### are computed in a fully left-handed (LH) basis.

### --- define the fermion content ---
fermions <- data.frame(
  name = c("quarks_L", "uptype_R", "downtype_R", "leptons_L", "chargedleptons_R",
           "neutrinos_R",
           "leonids_L", "lions_R", "chimeras_R", "apex_L", "highapex_R",
           "lowapex_R"),
  Y_L = c( 1/3,  0,  0, -1,  0, 0,
           -11/3, 0,  0, 1/2, 0, 0),
  Y_R = c( 0,  4/3, -2/3,  0, -2, 0,
           0, -8/3, -14/3,  0, 3/2, -1/2),
  d3 = c(3,  3,  3,  1,  1, 1,
          1,  1,  1,  8,  8, 8),
  d2 = c(2,  1,  1,  2,  1, 1,
          2,  1,  1,  2,  1, 1),
  Dynkinindex_SU3 = c(1/2, 1/2, 1/2,  0,  0, 0,
                     0,  0,  0,  3,  3, 3),
  Dynkinindex_SU2 = c(1/2,  0,  0, 1/2,  0, 0,
                     1/2,  0,  0, 1/2,  0, 0),
  Ngenerations = c(3, 3, 3, 4, 4, 4, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3)
)

### --- Helper: convert to LH basis ---
get_fields <- function(df) {
  left <- subset(df, Y_L != 0)
  left$Y_eff <- left$Y_L
  right <- subset(df, Y_R != 0)
  right$Y_eff <- -right$Y_R
  rbind(left, right)
}

### --- 1.  $[SU(3)]^2 U(1)$  anomaly ---
```

```

anom_SU3_SU3_U1 <- function(df) {
  fields <- get_fields(df)
  sum(fields$Y_eff * fields$Dynkinindex_SU3 * fields$d2 * fields$Ngenerations)
}

### --- 2. [SU(2)]2 U(1) anomaly ---
anom_SU2_SU2_U1 <- function(df) {
  fields <- get_fields(df)
  sum(fields$Y_eff * fields$Dynkinindex_SU2 * fields$d3 * fields$Ngenerations)
}

### --- 3. Gravitational-U(1) anomaly ---
anom_grav_U1 <- function(df) {
  fields <- get_fields(df)
  sum(fields$Y_eff * fields$d2 * fields$d3 * fields$Ngenerations)
}

### --- 4. [U(1)]3 anomaly ---
anom_U1_U1_U1 <- function(df) {
  fields <- get_fields(df)
  sum((fields$Y_eff^3) * fields$d2 * fields$d3 * fields$Ngenerations)
}

### --- Print anomaly results ---
cat("SU(3)^2 U(1) anomaly =", anom_SU3_SU3_U1(fermions), "\n")
cat("SU(2)^2 U(1) anomaly =", anom_SU2_SU2_U1(fermions), "\n")
cat("Grav^2 U(1) anomaly   =", anom_grav_U1(fermions), "\n")
cat("U(1)^3 anomaly       =", anom_U1_U1_U1(fermions), "\n")

```

The aureons: hypothetical particles associated with the golden ratios

The natural emergence of the golden ratio and its conjugate at the intersection of the left- and right-handed hypercharges—arising from two simple polynomials evaluated at integer seeds—is remarkable. The golden ratio has long been recognized as a bridge between mathematics, aesthetics, and nature. Historically, φ reflects the heritage of ancient Greece, with contributions from Euclid, Phidias, and the Pythagoreans, while the term *aurea* (golden)—inspiring the particle name *aureon*—acknowledges the Italian tradition surrounding this number, exemplified by Luca Pacioli, Leonardo Bonacci, and Leonardo da Vinci.

The aureons are hypothetical vector-like particles (Table 6) seeded at $k = k' = \varphi$ (positive aureons) or $k = k' = \varphi^*$ (negative aureons), each assumed to follow 3 generations. This assumption is motivated by analogy with the other fermionic families (excluding the electron due to its unique fundamental status). The aureons exist in both the left- and right-handed sectors, owing to their definite hypercharges: $Y_L(\varphi) = Y_R(\varphi) = -1 + \frac{2\sqrt{5}}{3}$ and $Y_L(\varphi^*) = Y_R(\varphi^*) = -1 - \frac{2\sqrt{5}}{3}$. However, both possess vanishing left-handed weak isospin: $T_3^L(\varphi, \varphi) = T_3^L(\varphi^*, \varphi^*) = 0$ which prevents them from forming a doublet in the left-handed sector (where $T_3^L = \pm \frac{1}{2}$ is required). The only consistent interpretation is to regard them as singlets in both chiral sectors—a situation not forbidden by the SM, though highly unconventional. Their masses are assumed here to follow the same mass law as other fermions, although this appears conceptually inconsistent given that the Higgs mechanism cannot couple two singlets. The quoted mass values in Table 6 should therefore be interpreted with caution. The gauge anomaly calculation is unaffected by the aureons due to $Y_L(\varphi) = Y_R(\varphi)$ and $Y_L(\varphi^*) = Y_R(\varphi^*)$.

The existence of the aureons raises several theoretical challenges. In particular, their hypercharges and related quantum numbers take irrational values, which has no precedent within the SM where all gauge charges are rational. This irrationality complicates their potential embedding into a consistent gauge structure and questions their compatibility with charge quantization. Remarkably, however, when the quantum numbers associated with φ and φ^* are summed, all irrational components cancel exactly — yielding to $Y^\pm = Y(\varphi) + Y(\varphi^*) = -2$, $Q^\pm = Q(\varphi) + Q(\varphi^*) = -1$, $L^\pm = L(\varphi) + L(\varphi^*) = 2$ and $B^\pm = B(\varphi) + B(\varphi^*) = 0$. This coincidence suggests that the two conjugate states might not be independent but rather complementary components of a deeper, possibly split structure. In such an interpretation, the apparent irrationality of each individual component could reflect an underlying symmetry or duality, only restored when both are considered together.

aureons		seeds			predicted mass (MeV)			quantum numbers		
		n	k	k'	if $n' = -1$	if $n' = 0$	if $n' = 1$	Y	L	B
positive aureons	Φ_1^+	1	φ	φ	1.795 ± 0.012	2.5155 ± 0.0093	3.524 ± 0.013	$-1 + \frac{2\sqrt{5}}{3}$	$1 - \frac{\sqrt{5}}{2}$	$\frac{\sqrt{5}}{6}$
	Φ_2^+	2	φ	φ	196.5 ± 1.0	275.29 ± 0.59	385.7 ± 1.4	$-1 + \frac{2\sqrt{5}}{3}$	$1 - \frac{\sqrt{5}}{2}$	$\frac{\sqrt{5}}{6}$
	Φ_3^+	3	φ	φ	21503 ± 81	30128 ± 42	42211 ± 190	$-1 + \frac{2\sqrt{5}}{3}$	$1 - \frac{\sqrt{5}}{2}$	$\frac{\sqrt{5}}{6}$
negative aureons	Φ_1^-	1	φ^*	φ^*	30.341 ± 0.056	34.074 ± 0.067	38.265 ± 0.079	$-1 - \frac{2\sqrt{5}}{3}$	$1 + \frac{\sqrt{5}}{2}$	$-\frac{\sqrt{5}}{6}$
	Φ_2^-	2	φ^*	φ^*	275.42 ± 0.43	309.30 ± 0.51	347.35 ± 0.61	$-1 - \frac{2\sqrt{5}}{3}$	$1 + \frac{\sqrt{5}}{2}$	$-\frac{\sqrt{5}}{6}$
	Φ_3^-	3	φ^*	φ^*	2500.1 ± 3.2	2807.7 ± 3.8	3153.1 ± 4.6	$-1 - \frac{2\sqrt{5}}{3}$	$1 + \frac{\sqrt{5}}{2}$	$-\frac{\sqrt{5}}{6}$

Table 6. Characteristics of the aureons. The names, symbols, seeds, predicted mass and quantum numbers of the hypothetical vectorial particles called the *aureons* (partitioned into the *positive* aureons and the *negative* aureons) are summarized here. Their left-handed weak isospin is $T_3^L = 0$ for all, and their electric charge follows $Q = \frac{Y}{2}$. Because n' is unknown (distributed between $-1, 0$ and 1), there are three possibilities for the mass of each aureon. Predicted masses correspond to median and 2.5th and 97.5th percentiles of predictions from $\sim 10^5$ sets of $(\alpha, \beta, \alpha', \beta'$ and $\lambda)$ that individually reproduce the observed masses of known fermions (PDG 2024) within experimental uncertainties (details in Table 3). The color of the aureons is currently undetermined.